

TrustNet: Trust-Based Networking

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Abstract—This paper presents and evaluates a novel network paradigm called Trust-Based Networking (TrustNet), which has been developed to address the growing complexity and challenges of trust in modern networks. The TrustNet framework relies on techniques such as belief function-based trust assessment, decentralised trust management, dynamic trust updates, and mechanisms for trustworthy communication between nodes to improve AI-driven path analysis, routing and network management. TrustNet is also architected to support larger-scale scalability through cluster-based parallelism. The experimental setup, implemented in the Graphical Network Simulator 3 (GNS3) emulation environment, includes Open vSwitches (OVSSs), Virtual Machines (VMs) and realistic router images. The evaluation focuses on operational metrics critical to trust-driven network services, such as network transmission time, overall convergence time, belief function execution time, trust verification latency across varying cluster sizes. Experimental results demonstrate TrustNet’s ability to maintain high levels of trustworthiness and operational efficiency in the presence of conflicting or inconsistent trust evidence. These findings highlight TrustNet’s potential to redefine networking paradigms by integrating trust as a core component of network management, ensuring robust and adaptive networks.

Keywords—AI, networking, routing, trust, management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a transformative force in the realm of networking, enabling smarter, more efficient, and highly adaptive network management. From traffic optimization and anomaly detection to predictive maintenance and self-healing networks, AI-driven solutions are reshaping how networked devices operate [1]. This evolution has led to the proliferation of AI-enabled network devices, which utilize advanced algorithms to autonomously analyze data, make decisions, and execute actions in real-time. In critical networking scenarios, trust in AI systems is pivotal to ensure that

devices perform as expected, even under dynamic or adverse conditions [2]. AI systems must consistently perform their intended functions, even under different or adverse conditions [3]. Several factors influence trust in AI for network applications. These include the interpretability of AI decisions, the robustness against adversarial attacks, the ability of the system to deal with biased data, and ethical concerns [4]. In networking, where decisions can impact connectivity, resource allocation or security, explainability is critical. However, AI systems often operate as *opaque boxes* and can make decisions that are difficult to interpret [5]. Therefore, providing clear insights into how the AI arrives at its conclusions can allow stakeholders to evaluate and trust the system’s outcomes.

The integration of AI into networking has introduced transformative capabilities, enabling automation, efficiency, and real-time decision-making. AI-enabled network devices can optimize resource allocation, manage traffic dynamically, and enhance security through intelligent anomaly detection [6]. At the same time, a lack of reliability in such systems results can undermine trust and lead to a reluctance to adopt AI-driven solutions, especially in mission-critical environments such as healthcare, finance or defense. For example, centralized AI often struggles with scalability, latency and resilience. As the size and complexity of the network increases, the centralized architecture can become a bottleneck and lead to delays in trust assessments and routing decisions. In addition, a centralized system represents a single point of failure and poses security, trust and reliability risks if the central system is compromised [7]. On the other hand, edge-based AI models can distribute the evaluation of trust and the decision-making processes to network nodes such as routers or edge devices. By processing trust assessments locally, edge-based AI reduces dependency on centralized systems and improves scalability and resilience [8]. However, edge-based AI systems are often limited in terms of computing power and can lead to inconsistencies in trust evaluation, as different nodes may prioritize different criteria or have access to different

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Fig. 1: Routers with AI capabilities in the network can calculate contradictory routing paths as their decisions.

information. This fragmentation can lead to inconsistent routing decisions, which can affect the overall efficiency of the network.

II. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION FOR TRUST-BASED NETWORKING

A. Issues in Edge Routing with AI

Figure 1 shows a multi-domain network architecture in which several Autonomous Systems (AS-1, AS-2, AS-3) are connected to routers that use AI-based routing decisions. The figure shows three possible paths (Path-1, Path-2, and Path-3) between Router-1 and a data center in AS-3. Each path is evaluated by the AI at the edge nodes, which assign probabilities reflecting the trustworthiness of the paths based on various factors such as latency, congestion, or past performance. However, there are several challenges to this scenario. First, the variability of path probabilities between different routers can lead to inconsistent decisions. For example, Router-1 assigns the highest trust to Path-1 (93%), while Router-2 prioritizes Path-3 (95%) based on its local AI analysis. This discrepancy in probability assignments can lead to inconsistencies in routing decisions, resulting in *suboptimal or conflicting data flows*. Secondly, a lack of global coordination between the AI systems of different routers can lead to inefficiencies. Since each router operates independently, *the lack of a unified trust assessment* across the network leads to fragmented decision making. This fragmentation can lead to bottlenecks or increased latency if the routers prioritize different paths.

The AI models in the edge routers do provide initial probability calculations for path selection, but their ability to adapt to rapid changes in the network is limited without real-time updates from other nodes or a centralized coordination mechanism. The multi-domain

nature of the modern networks brings challenges in interoperability and trust assessment. Path-2 in Figure 1, for example, spans three autonomous systems (AS-1, AS-2, AS-3), which requires trust assessments in different administrative domains with different policies, metrics, and standards. This lack of standardization can undermine the accuracy of trust-based routing decisions and increase the complexity of ensuring secure and reliable communication. Although AI-assisted routing can offer significant potential to improve trust in path selection strategy, issues such as conflicting probability assessments, lack of coordination, limited adaptability to real-time conditions, and interoperability between multiple domains need to be addressed to fully realize the benefits. In this paper, we propose a mechanism for global trust coordination, dynamic trust updates, and the use of standardized trust metrics to effectively address these challenges.

B. Motivation for a Trust-Based Approach

Trust is essential to AI-native network management, enabling secure, context-aware operations and resilience against cascading failures from compromised devices. In highly dynamic environments such as edge and multi-domain networks, trust must be continuously evaluated and integrated into automated decision processes. While prior work [4], [5], [9] has explored AI or trust independently, TrustNet introduces a novel architecture that unifies belief-based trust fusion (e.g., Dempster-Shafer Theory (DST)), AI-guided path analysis, and decentralized cluster-level aggregation. Unlike isolated or sensor-centric trust systems (e.g., [10], [11]), TrustNet enables scalable and resilient trust computation through modular integration of localized AI decisions, trust evidence sharing, and belief fusion within temporary clusters. This tight coupling of trust and AI-driven routing supports dynamic service provisioning, enhances security, and enables trust-based path filtering, allowing network services to adapt in real time based on the trustworthiness of participants.

To contextualize the contributions of TrustNet, it is important to contrast it with two major categories of prior work: (i) Knowledge-defined network architectures that emphasize performance optimization but typically omit explicit trust modelling, and (ii) DST-based trust systems such as DUEL [10] and multi-sensor fusion schemes [11] that focus on belief assignment without integrating routing or scalability concerns. Table I presents a unified comparison of these approaches, high-

Fig. 2: The proposed trust layer combines the individual AI results within the cluster and computes a single trusted path for the cluster.

lighting TrustNet’s distinct architecture, fusion logic, and deployment realism. In particular, TrustNet tightly couples belief-based trust scoring with routing decisions, supports decentralized cluster-level trust aggregation, and introduces revocation mechanisms based on time decay and trust disagreement, features absent in prior DST-based models.

III. TRUST-BASED NETWORKING ARCHITECTURE

In a trust-based networking system, *trust evidence* refers to observable indicators such as packet delivery rates, link delay, or behavioral history that help evaluate the reliability of entities or paths. This raw evidence is processed using a *belief function* such as DST, which assigns degrees of belief to different hypotheses: “Trust,” “Distrust,” and “Uncertainty.” For instance, if a path demonstrates high delivery success but moderate latency, the system might assign 70% to “Trust,” 10% to “Distrust,” and 20% to “Uncertainty.” These evaluations, collected from multiple nodes, are then aggregated into a global trust score to guide routing or system decisions.

A. High-Level Design and Key Benefits

Figure 2 illustrates the high-level structure of the TrustNet architecture, which augments conventional network stacks, comprising data, control, and management

planes, with a dedicated *trust layer*. Traditional infrastructures often lack mechanisms to dynamically evaluate node trustworthiness. TrustNet addresses this gap by integrating belief-function-enabled registries [13], distributed trust scoring, and path-level monitoring. This trust layer can ensure secure, transparent, and resilient operations without relying on centralized authorities, instead using rotating cluster leaders and decentralized trust coordination mechanisms. TrustNet mainly introduces several key features:

- (i) *Decentralized Trust Profiles*: Each network path is associated with a dynamic trust profile, i.e., a structured representation of node behavior over time, maintained in distributed registries. Profiles may include performance metrics, compliance indicators, and historical trust assessments.
- (ii) *Belief-Based Trust Mechanism*: TrustNet employs a belief function (e.g., DST) to fuse multiple trust inputs into a consistent assessment. Each node computes local trust values, while designated cluster leaders aggregate them to form a global view. This collective evaluation supports decentralized and adaptive routing decisions.
- (iii) *Path Revocation*: If a path behaves maliciously or deviates from policy, its trust score is downgraded and its usage restricted. This revocation is driven by

TABLE I: Comparison of TrustNet vs Knowledge-Defined Networking and Prior DST-Based Systems

Feature	Knowledge-Defined Networking (KDN) [12]	Prior DST-Based Systems (DUEL [10] / Sensor Fusion [11])	TrustNet
1. Application Domain and Design Goals			
Target Environment	General-purpose network optimization (latency, throughput)	Overlay routing / sensor trust estimation	AI-native, multi-domain trust-aware networks
Trust Handling	Not addressed, as the focus is on performance optimization and automation, not trust or security.	Localized belief estimation, not integrated with path selection	Explicit trust fusion drives routing decisions and node revocation
2. DST Usage and Fusion Logic			
Fusion Level	Not applicable	Node-level only	Cluster-level hierarchical fusion with domain-local coordination
Conflict Resolution	Not applicable	Basic averaging or ignored conflict	Dempster's Rule with conflict co-efficient handling
Leader Coordination	Not applicable	Centralized controller or static roles	Temporary cluster leaders perform fusion; coordination is decentralized and rotating
3. System Architecture			
Routing Integration	High-level goal: uses ML inference for performance-driven decisions (QoS, dynamic routing)	Loose or absent	Trust scores to be used in path selection, filtering, and caching
Scalability Approach	Relies on SDN's logically centralized control plane for a global state view	Static topology or centralized overlay	Decentralized clustering with asynchronous, parallel trust fusion
Revocation Support	Not addressed	Not addressed	Time decay, disagreement-based revocation at trust plane
4. Evaluation Realism			
Implementation	Simulated network or testbed only	Simulation (OMNeT++, NS2, etc.)	GNS3-based: real router images, Open vSwitch, IPsec, VM coordination

disagreement among nodes or decaying trust over time.

- (iv) *Fault Tolerance via Redundancy*: Trust data can be replicated across distributed Data Centers (DCs) operated by Internet Service Providers (ISPs) or Mobile Network Operators (MNOs). In case of failure, a secondary DC can ensure service continuity by maintaining synchronized trust registries.

TrustNet fundamentally differs from traditional AI-based approaches, such as *knowledge-defined networking* [12], by embedding trust directly into routing and decision-making. While prior trust systems often rely on binary models or probabilistic inference, TrustNet uses belief functions such as DST to account for conflicting and uncertain evidence. This allows more robust and context-aware evaluations, especially critical in edge and AI-native networks where trust inputs may originate from heterogeneous sources (e.g., anomaly detection, historical performance, external reputation scores). By integrating trust scoring into AI-driven path selection, TrustNet enables prioritization of interactions with trustworthy nodes, detection of compromised links, and resilience in multi-domain or adversarial scenarios.

B. Cluster Formation and Structure

The criteria for selecting a cluster in a group of routers may vary depending on the specific implementation and goals of the algorithm. A lightweight, cluster-based architecture can be used to scale trust computations across routers. The formation of clusters can be controlled by different strategies, including (i) topological proximity (e.g., all direct neighbours), (ii) random selection of neighbours, or (iii) manual assignment via network management tools.

Each cluster includes a designated leader responsible for aggregating trust evidence from member nodes and performing belief fusion (e.g., via DST) to compute a collective trust score. While all nodes compute local trust values based on their own AI-derived observations, only the cluster leader performs the final trust fusion, ensuring internal consistency while minimizing communication and processing overhead. Leader coordination is achieved through message exchange within the cluster, and the communication load remains minimal due to the summary nature of exchanged evidence. Although fault-tolerant leader election or dynamic rotation is not currently implemented, the architecture is compatible

with such extensions, e.g., through trust-ranked or round-robin selection, allowing resilience against leader failure in future deployments.

C. Trust Score Calculation and Node Interaction

Figure 3 illustrates the trust-based routing mechanism within TrustNet, where three routers (Router-1, Router-2, and Router-3) collaborate to assess the trustworthiness of two candidate paths (Path-1 and Path-2) to a data center. Each router independently performs AI-based path analysis using local observations such as latency, anomalies, or past performance. These evaluations are exchanged as *AI Analysis Messages* (yellow envelopes), carrying path reliability estimates. Upon receiving these, routers execute a *Belief Function Analysis* using DST to fuse the evidence and compute trust scores. TrustNet computes belief scores over three hypotheses, Trust (T), Distrust (D), and Uncertainty (U), and guides path selection based on the highest aggregated belief. The trust assessments are then shared via *Trust Messages* (blue envelopes), enabling synchronized, trust-aware routing decisions across the cluster. The sequence (1) *Local AI analysis* => (2) *yellow message exchange* => (3) *belief fusion* => (4) *trust message exchange* ensures that routing reflects a shared, robust view of trustworthiness based on distributed evidence.

For example, in Figure 3, three routers can independently assess the trustworthiness of two paths. Each assigns local trust, distrust, and uncertainty values. TrustNet’s fusion engine, hosted at one cluster node, aggregates

these values while factoring in agreement levels and conflict. In this example, Path-1 yields a high trust score (85%) due to consensus; Path-2, facing conflicting inputs, results in lower trust (50%). This fusion enables consistent, decentralized trust reasoning. TrustNet can also handle conflicting or low confidence evidence by assigning a higher uncertainty mass (the measure of how much the system “does not know” about a trust decision) and down-weighting contradictory sources during fusion. In highly uncertain cases, belief values do not exceed trust thresholds and such paths can be deprioritised. Trust thresholds or decay mechanisms can also be used to permanently revoke untrusted nodes. The trust layer in TrustNet complements conventional routing, enhancing both security and reliability. It dynamically adapts to changing network conditions, ensuring that packets are forwarded over the most trustworthy paths. By combining distributed assessments, TrustNet enables robust routing even under incomplete or inconsistent information. Finally, the end-to-end workflow of TrustNet, showing belief collection, mapping, and decision-making with continuous feedback, is summarized in Figure 3.

IV. TRUSTNET SERVICES AND APPLICATIONS

A. Service Models

By leveraging trust assessments and scores, network services can dynamically adapt to the reliability, behavior, and context of users, devices, and applications. This results in a more secure, responsive, and intelligent network environment where resources are allocated based on trustworthiness, activity, and service requirements [9]. Compared to traditional static orchestration approaches, TrustNet provides a more dynamic framework for service provisioning. In Internet of Things (IoT) networks, trust scores can be assigned to IoT devices based on attributes such as their capabilities, firmware integrity, and compliance with security policies. These trust scores can control the provision of network services and ensure that only trusted devices have access to key network resources. In industrial automation, production processes can be optimized by assessing the trustworthiness of network nodes responsible for critical tasks. In mobile edge computing, trusted assessments of edge devices can provide resource allocation decisions for specific tasks based on their computing power, latency and historical performance. TrustNet can further enhance vehicular networks by enabling trust-based dynamic routing that leverages the reputation and trust values of network nodes to ensure secure and efficient communication [14].

Fig. 3: The TrustNet performs trust evidence collection, belief mapping, and decision-making with continuous feedback.

B. Use Case Scenario and Scalability Aspects

Consider a scenario where two routing paths are available between a client endpoint and a core data center hosting a critical service: Path-A consists of routers with high trust scores (for example, 0.85) based on firmware integrity, compliance history, and consistent behavior, while Path-B offers lower latency but includes a newly deployed edge router with a low trust score (for example, 0.55) due to an incomplete security verification. While traditional routing protocols might prioritize Path-B due to its low latency, TrustNet evaluates both options using a belief function that incorporates aggregated trust metrics and selects Path-A to ensure continuity of service over a more secure route. This trust-aware routing approach enables ISPs to maintain operational integrity and adhere to strict service level agreements, even in complex multi-domain environments.

From the large-scale scalability perspective on the communication side, the primary scalability constraint stems from inter-node message exchanges for AI analysis and trust aggregation. As the number of routers increases, transmission and convergence times grow due to added communication overhead. However, this is addressed in TrustNet by localizing trust computation within clusters (to avoid the exponential growth of power set combinations even in networks with many nodes) and using parallel trust propagation, limiting the impact on overall network convergence.

V. EVALUATION AND RESULTS

A. Test Setup

The test setup was implemented in the Graphical Network Simulator 3 (GNS3) emulation environment, as shown in our previous study [15], for a proof-of-concept implementation. The TrustNet architecture was evaluated using a network of 4 OpenvSwitches (OVSs) configured within GNS3. We selected DST as the belief function in our analysis. Note that, other belief functions (not as part of the our proof-of-concept evaluation) can also be possible options for evaluations. Additionally, 4 Virtual Machines (VMs) (or nodes) with Ubuntu 16 LTS were deployed and connected to each OVSs. In GNS3, OVS images that are installed in VM, are used to create an Open Shortest Path First (OSPF) network and routers are connected to the same OSPF area (area 0). Each of these VMs has capability of AI-based decision making (e.g. selecting the service routing path). Each node, implemented as a VM, computes local trust scores

Fig. 4: Aggregated trust calculation for a cluster with 4 nodes and 2 separate paths determines the best path when routers choose conflicting paths.

for candidate paths. These scores are transmitted to a designated cluster leader VM, which then performs belief fusion using a Python implementation of the DST algorithm.

Basically, there are 4 nodes and these nodes calculate 2 different paths as optimal paths, namely path-1 and path-2. In the implementation for the presented designed 4 OVS router network, there are two routes to reach a point according to OSPF. Each OVS sends the first two rows of its routing table to the cluster leader router in a 6 KB text message. The cluster leader was determined manually. Probability values for routes were entered manually on each OVS router. *Scapy* and *Numpy* libraries were used for messaging in the Python scripts, and the belief function calculations.

B. Results

Since the most valuable decision is given by the T (Trust) value calculation we have only used that parameter to assess the operational efficiency and responsiveness of the TrustNet system. Figure 4 illustrates the process of aggregate trust calculation with our selected belief function which is DST for a cluster consisting of four nodes (node-1, node-2, node-3 and node-4), each of which is assigned its own trust values for two possible paths (path-1 and path-2). For example, node-2 assigns the highest confidence value of 0.94 to path-1, while node-4 assigns a lower confidence value of 0.56. Similarly, node-3 assigns the highest trust value of 0.75 to path-2, followed by node-1 with 0.71. These individual scores illustrate the variability of the trust assignments between the nodes. With DST, the individual trust values are aggregated to calculate a unified trust value for each path. The aggregation process takes into account both

Fig. 5: The number of routers in the cluster impact the belief computation metrics (transmission time, convergence time, DST execution time)

agreement and disagreement between nodes, ensuring a robust assessment of the overall trustworthiness of each path. For Path-1, the aggregated trust score is 0.72, reflecting higher trust in this route. In contrast, Path-2 receives a lower aggregate trust score (0.28) compared to Path-1. The evaluation results show that path-1 is the more trustworthy route based on the collective evaluations and is therefore the preferred choice for data transmission.

Figure 5 shows the performance evaluation of the combined belief computation for two paths when the number of routers in a cluster increases. Three important metrics are measured: *network transmission time*, *Overall Convergence Time*, and *DST Execution Time*. The *network transmission time* indicates the time required to exchange information between the routers in the cluster, the overall convergence time refers to the total time required for the cluster to compute the combined belief values and reach a consistent state across all routers, and the DST execution time measures the computation time required for belief combination using the DST. As the number of routers increases, the *network transmission time* gradually increases. It starts at 11.31 seconds for 1 router and increases to 14.62 seconds for 8 routers. This reflects the additional communication overhead introduced by the increased cluster size. The overall convergence time starts at 11.311 seconds for 1 router and steadily increases to 14.625 seconds for 8 routers. The trend mirrors the *network transmission time*, as the communication overhead makes a significant contribution to convergence. Our selected belief function execution time is significantly lower compared to the other metrics. It starts at 0.001 milliseconds for 1 router and increases

slightly to 0.005 milliseconds for 8 routers. This slight increase shows how efficient the DST calculation is, even when the cluster size increases.

C. Discussion

The numerical results in Figure 4 illustrate the operational efficiency of TrustNet and its ability to balance security and dynamic service provisioning. The trust aggregation approach using the selected DST-based belief function enables adaptive path selection in networks, particularly in environments such as vehicular systems or IoT, where trust and connectivity vary over time. By fusing local trust evaluations, DST ensures that final trust scores are robust and resilient to isolated errors or noise, thereby supporting reliable decision-making. Key insights from Figure 5 include: (i) Network transmission time is the dominant contributor to overall convergence time, confirming its critical impact; (ii) DST execution time remains negligible compared to communication delays, highlighting its suitability for real-time or near-real-time applications; and (iii) DST computation scales efficiently with cluster size, showing minimal increase with added routers, whereas communication overhead grows linearly, suggesting that optimized data exchange protocols could enhance scalability.

TrustNet increases security through trust-based path selection, but introduces a new processing layer that can impact latency in ultra-reliable or time-sensitive scenarios. To counteract latency concerns, TrustNet uses lightweight DST-based fusion and decentralised, parallel cluster-based trust computation. While the current implementation does not include selective filtering, caching, or predictive modeling, these mechanisms can be incorporated in future work to further optimise low-latency routing decisions. Note that, while explicit adversarial attacks such as Sybil or lying nodes are not simulated, TrustNet's cluster-based belief fusion mitigates such behaviours through conflict-aware aggregation.

D. Challenges and Limitations

Even though TrustNet framework provides a trust-centric networking paradigm that integrates dynamic trust evaluations into routing and network management to ensure secure, reliable, and adaptive communication across heterogeneous and dynamic environments, several challenges can also be anticipated. (i) Ensuring seamless communication and consistent trust calculation across different architectures (e.g. IoT, vehicle networks or

cloud systems) remains a challenge. (ii) The need for robust confidence computations leads to trade-offs. While DST-based trust combining is computationally efficient, the time required to securely transmit and process trust data increases with the size of the cluster, potentially limiting the responsiveness of the system. (iii) Trust calculations in TrustNet depend on both static parameters and real-time data. On the other hand, as network conditions evolve frequently than the decision making and propagation times, ensuring that trust scores are promptly updated while maintaining system stability presents a significant challenge. (iv) Edge-based trust evaluations rely on routers with potentially limited computational power and memory. This constraint can limit the accuracy and scalability of trust calculations, particularly in larger or resource-constrained clusters.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presents TrustNet, a trust-based networking paradigm aimed at enhancing security, reliability, and adaptability across dynamic, AI-enabled network environments. The core innovation of TrustNet lies in its architectural integration of DST-based belief fusion at the cluster level, enabling decentralized trust aggregation and consistent routing decisions without central coordination. Compared to traditional routing, TrustNet introduces a lightweight trust layer that increases path selection robustness with less than a 5% increase in convergence time, while significantly improving trust-based decision confidence. Although our experiments use OSPF for demonstration, TrustNet is designed to be routing-protocol agnostic. Its trust assessment and evidence aggregation layers can operate orthogonally to the underlying routing logic, allowing seamless integration with traditional protocols, as well as with modern programmable and SDN-based routing schemes.

Future work may include benchmarking delay and energy costs, integrating timeliness-aware weighting to reduce historical bias, and evaluating TrustNet under adversarial conditions. The architecture of TrustNet can also be aligned with trust standardisation efforts by encoding belief evidence in formats such as JSON-LD or CBOR (e.g. IETF SCITT), using decentralised identifiers (e.g. W3C DIDs, Verifiable Credentials) and adopting ontology-based semantics (e.g. ETSI ZSM) to enable interoperability between domains and secure integration into autonomous network infrastructures.

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VII. BIOGRAPHIES

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